

R&D PROGRAM FOR INNOVATIVE CIVIL AIRCRAFT STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT: The pressure to save energy is intense as ever due to limited energy supply and global environmental problems such as CO₂ gas. On the other hand, economic growth and a high quality of life demands high-speed transportation. However, energy saving is not so well advanced in progress in the transportation field. Weight reduction for vehicles is a direct solution. This program was implemented in 1999 to reduce vehicle weight, setting aircraft structure as the subject. The R&D program “key technology for innovative low-cost and light structures”, consists of the first 3 year “technology establishment phase” and the latter 2 year “technology verification phase”. The wing and nose structures have numerous part count in an aircraft ; thus, the target is determined as 50% and 80% part-count-reduction for the wing and nose structures respectively. Developed technologies are Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VaRTM), co-cured CFRP structures, new-type sandwich panel consisting of plastic core and CFRP for composite structure, and thin, large-size precision casting for D357 Al alloy, friction stir welding for 2024 and 7075 Al alloy and super-plastic forming for 5083 Al alloy. The intended target is 15% and 10% weight-reduction for the wing and nose structures respectively. Full-scale test articles are in progress and static, fatigue, pressurization tests, and bird strike test will be performed as final activities. The program has been reviewed, evaluated and simulated certification process is now being performed through DER (Designated Engineering Representative)’s review. This paper is an interim report at the end of March 2003.

KEYWORD: co-cured CFRP structures, light-weight structures, wing structure, nose structure, civil aircraft structures

INTRODUCTION

Economic growth and a high quality of life demands high-speed transportation. However the pressure to save energy is as intense as before due to both the limited energy supply and global environmental problems such as greenhouse gases emission. Energy saving is in progress in the industrial field, but a quarter of energy is consumed in the transportation field and the increasing ratio of energy consumption in that field is relatively high. In order to overcome the situation and to decrease energy consumption, weight reduction for vehicles is necessary. A five-year NEDO open-bidding program “R&D of Key Technologies of Design and Manufacturing for Innovative Light Structures” was implemented in 1999. The purpose of the program is to reduce vehicle weight, to save energy and to reduce greenhouse gases through R&D and its application to various vehicles.

In the program, we determined the weight reduction targets as 15% for the wing structure and 10% for the nose structure compared with conventional aluminum alloy structures with the most low-cost design. The structures of an aircraft are predominantly made by the built-up method in which many parts are assembled by rivets and fasteners, so the part count is an extraordinarily large number. Reducing part-count is the most effective way to reduce costs because it reduces time for fabrication, assembling and processing. In the program, we selected the wing structure and the nose structure as

representative portions since they have a large number of parts and complicated figures. The wing structure is sensitive to strength and acts as the fuel tank. The nose structure has the pressurized space. The part-count reduction targets are set at 50% and 80% respectively.

OVERVIEW

1. Organization of the program

Five companies were entrusted jointly with the program from NEDO (New Energy and Industrial Technology Development Organization). KHI (Kawasaki Heavy Industries, Ltd.), FHI (Fuji Heavy Industries Ltd.), NIPPI (NIPPI Corporation, former Japan Aircraft Mfg. Co. Ltd.) and MHI (Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, Ltd.) are in charge of R&D in nose, wing, leading-edge, fuselage panel structures respectively. JADC (Japan Aircraft Development Corporation) collaborates in R&D with other members through conferences to review activities and audits. Additionally, a national laboratory and a college collaborate on the program as shown in Fig. 1. NAL (National Aerospace Laboratory) will aim at an adequate strength assessment for composite structures made by new processing. KIT (Kanazawa Institute of Technology) will aim at prediction of fatigue life of the composite materials used in the program.

Fig. 1 Organization Chart of the R&D Program (FY2003)

2. Approaching methods

The program is five-years. Using the “Building Block Approach” method we expect a steady technological approach to the goal. In the beginning of the program, we concentrated on steady steps. We intended to perform the same procedures as in the actual development of a new aircraft. We made a plan, and considered the following important items: (a) a design based on firm procedures, specifications etc.; (b) technical assessment; and (c) assessment of a substantiation test by a DER. To assess the design and its validity, we examined the design standards and adopted FAR Part 25, Advisory Circulars and supplemented documents as a design rule for a commercial airplane [1].

Full-scale component articles fabricated by March 2003 are shown in Fig. 2.

RESULT OF WING, NOSE AND LEADING-EDGE STRUCTURES

1. Development for wing structure

The wing box structure will be built-up from three parts using a small number of fasteners. The lower-box structure bond-assembly was fabricated through co-bonding skin, VaRTM stringers, rib intercostals and two RTM spars in one cure process. Upper panel bond-assembly will be fabricated

Fig.2 Building Blocks and Interim Result up to Mar. 2003

through co-bonding skin, VaRTM stringers and rib intercostals in one cure process. Each rib web is one-piece laminated part. See Fig. 3-4.

In developing, RTM, VaRTM and stiffened co-bond panels with unique RTM stringers have been made with new RTM resin and carbon fiber textiles [2-3]. Intensive case studies for structural concept have been conducted. At first “Integrated Stiffened Panel Box Structure” was selected. The stringer type was studied and changed from blade-shape to hat-shape in consideration of weight reduction. A comparative study with compression after impact (CAI) tests had been conducted to investigate the improvement of damage tolerance performance by simply stitched laminates. It is important to find out the practical and effective level of stitching density. In RTM process, one of the most important characteristics is “low viscosity” of the resin and need to provide a proper resin flow. This is especially important to realize large RTM parts. Simulation analysis using Darcy’s law has provided proper planning to set input/output ports and flow path of the resin for large RTM parts. The new RTM resin has another feature to accept a 2-stage cure process. The parts’ shapes can be fixed at the initial low temperature cure stage. Then, the parts can be handled as free-standing (without complicated shape-constrained jigs) in the second high temperature stage. A unique hybrid co-bonding process has been created with this feature. Prepreg with low cost tough resin can be laminated by automated tow placement. Adhesive films and the first stage cured RTM stringers/spars will be set on the raw skin without complicated support jigs, and then cured simultaneously. VaRTM is used for stringers and RTM for spars in consideration of accuracy and low-cost. Specimens of the bonding surface between the prepreg and the RTM were checked for strength in Mode-I and II. A compressive strength test with stiffened panel was conducted and no hazardous pre-mature debonding was found up to design compressive strain level. The wing box structure acts as the fuel tank. A fuel exposure test will be gotten effectively by using the AGATE (NASA’s Advanced General Aviation Transportation Experiments) test matrix. Lightning protection tests usually will need one specimen for each design feature: thinnest skin, fuel vent, leading edge and

Fig. 3 Baseline Structural Concept of the Wing Structure

Fig. 4 Manufacturing Flow for the Wing Structure

low-cost. Specimens of the bonding surface between the prepreg and the RTM were checked for strength in Mode-I and II. A compressive strength test with stiffened panel was conducted and no hazardous pre-mature debonding was found up to design compressive strain level. The wing box structure acts as the fuel tank. A fuel exposure test will be gotten effectively by using the AGATE (NASA’s Advanced General Aviation Transportation Experiments) test matrix. Lightning protection tests usually will need one specimen for each design feature: thinnest skin, fuel vent, leading edge and

attachment to forward spar, skin/spar joint, and fuel filler cap. Tests will be required for new designs or changes in materials or conductive paths.

2. Development for nose structure

The nose skin panels will be replaced by CFRP sandwich panels, which consist of CFRP skins and foam cores. A full-scale component article of left hand and right hand side portions of an upper sandwich panel structure was fabricated as shown in Fig.2. On the other hand, new aluminum alloy technologies are applied in nose structures. Large size, aluminum precision sand casting shown in Fig.2 were developed and will be applied to the one-piece cockpit pressure floor support structure and so on. Friction stir welding technology was developed and will be applied to the pressure bulkhead structure and so on.

Detailed results of the development were described by Y. Hirose[4-5]. To sum up, the development of metal-related technologies was successfully completed by FY 2000(March, 2001) and recent development has been focused on CFRP sandwich panels and the main verification test will be done by the full-scale static pressurization test. The limit load per FAR 25.365 is $(56.1\text{kPa} (8.14\text{lb/in}^2) \times 1.33)$ which is the pressure differential load corresponding to maximum relief valve setting $\times 1.33$. A dummy windshield must be designed to simulate the structural characteristics of the actual windshield glass. There is discontinuity in this area and it is prone to fatigue due to pressurization and depressurization. FAA officers suggested that any good plan such as loosening the fasteners adjacent to the dummy windshield is necessary not to give the load to the windshield in the static pressurization test. A DER suggested that the boundary areas of the windshield must be assessed during the test, and if possible compared with Finite Element Analysis as far as the stress concentration is concerned.

3. Development for leading-edge structure

The new concept of the leading edge structure consists of a forward panel formed from 5083 superplastic aluminum alloy sheets and an aft support cast from D357 high strength aluminum alloy. The panel has corrugated inner skin as a hot air duct

Fig. 5 Structural Concept of the Leading Edge

for anti-icing, and is expected to resist a bird-strike with large deformed energy absorption. The aft support is cast by investment method as a monolithic structure with complex and thin webs. The forward panels and aft supports are welded span-wise respectively.

To verify the new design concept, manufacturing trials were performed. Many new technologies were adopted, tried and established. Ultrasonic spot welding was adopted for producing the surface of the forward panel like a mirror. Magnetic stirring TIG welding is used for the cast. The most effort was focused on designing against a bird strike test. It is important to avoid damage to the anti-ice tube and the hazardous fracture of the casting during the 320-knot bird impact, not to give damage to the wing front spar web. Improvement was done by structural modification decreasing/splitting bird impact, large energy absorption to the forward panel, and rearrangement of the anti-ice tube. See Fig. 5. The stress analysis of structure was performed using FEM. And to verify the structural integrity, a 4 lbs bird strike test was conducted at the velocity of 325kt. The results of tests were no penetration (no rupture) of the leading edge, no breakage/fragments of the after-support casting structure, and no signs of damage of the anti-ice tube. The improvement of structure was confirmed. DER's comment was that the test has shown the integrity of the structure and the basic structure is certifiable.

RESULT OF SUPPORTING RESEARCHES

1. Researches by accelerated test method

The accelerated test method by Y. Miyano[6] is becoming a powerful analyzing tool for evaluating and predicting long-term durability, when the candidate composite materials are applicable to the accelerated test methodology. The method is effective in points of testing time and its expense. In the actual airplane development phase, a real-time, full-scale fatigue test is necessary for its demonstration. In this section, the following results will be introduced : (1) Recent results by accelerated test methods, (2) A preliminary evaluation of the durability and the reliability of the composite laminates (3) A preliminary test result of the influences of water absorption on the time-temperature dependent flexural behavior. (4) Post-impact fatigue performance test using CFRP laminate test specimens, will be conducted as one of the flaw-growth tests.

(1) The dynamic viscoelastic test, constant-strain rate (CSR) bending test, and creep bending test were conducted for three kinds of CFRP laminates, UT500/#135, T800S-24k/#3900-2B, and T800S-24k/TR-A33, which are candidate materials for wing and nose structures. (See Fig.6.) The time-temperature superposition principle holds for flexural CSR strengths of these CFRP laminates. (See Fig.7.) Each time-temperature shift factor agrees well with that of the storage modulus of corresponding CFRP laminates. The flexural creep strength can be predicted from the master curve of CSR strength for each CFRP laminate based on the linear cumulative damage law.

(2) The durability and the reliability of three kinds of CFRP laminates were evaluated using the self-developed durability analysis software which is based on two analytical methods; the accelerated testing methodology and the probabilistic treatment of creep rupture behavior[7-8]. (See Fig.8.) A preliminary evaluation suggests that all three material systems had sufficient durability under the given loads based on "TWIST". (See Fig.9.) No predicted probabilities of failure were over 10^{-12} . It means the probability of failure against 20 years (75,000 flights) would be fewer than 10^{-12} in each case.

(3) The influences of water absorption on the time-temperature dependent flexural behavior of unidirectional CFRP laminate were studied. The creep compliance of CFRP laminates decrease with the increasing of water content as well as time and temperature. The time-temperature superposition principle holds for the creep compliance of CFRP laminate regardless of water absorption.

(4) According to K. Hirano's report[9], post-impact fatigue life with open-hole specimens is extremely degraded when the cycles are over 10^5 in some kinds of polymer matrix composite material, e.g. IM600/PIXA-M, G40-800/5260. Those phenomena are different upon material types. That suggested the need to clarify and confirm the phenomena for the candidate materials after low-velocity impact damage (non-visible damage). The research result may suggest no fatigue limit and would give the decision whether no-growth design is applicable

Fig. 6 Fiber geometry of CFRP (laminates)

Fig. 7 Time-Temperature Superposition

Fig. 8 Outline of the reliability analysis

Fig. 9 Flight Pattern of Load and Temperature

Fig. 10 Recent Post Impact Fatigue Data

or not. Preliminary test results suggest a fatigue threshold does not exist as shown in Fig.10.

2. Researches by strength assessment testing method for advanced composite material

T. Ishikawa leads researches to develop standardized testing methods, and to develop advanced testing techniques in order to realize the next-generation aerospace vehicles[10]. In our program, RTM with braided carbon fiber textiles and stitching is used. The merits of RTM are the low-cost and high interlaminar fracture toughness. To confirm the effects of RTM, the testing method must be considered and may be developed to compare with normal CFRP prepreg laminate.

The interlaminar shear strength of the unidirectional CF/EP composite measured by the compressive loading method of a double-notched specimen is reported. (Interlaminar shear strength result: almost the same)

Open Hole Compression (OHC) strength is conducted to see the difference of the rupture mechanism. Experimental in-situ observation during the test was intended by using a fiber-optic microscope with video-recording. In-situ observation revealed that fiber micro buckling in 0-layer starts early and the same result was confirmed by 2-D FEM. (OHC result: almost the same)

The NAL's double cantilever beam (DCB) tests were executed for stitched CFRP laminates to obtain relationships between mode I strain energy release rate (G_{IC}) and stitch density. The stitch parameters (stitch pitch and stitch spacing) and stitch thread (Kevlar) were changed and their effects on G_{IC} were examined by DCB tests and FEM analyses. It can be concluded that G_{IC} values were mainly governed by stitch density in linear relationships and the G_{IC} increasing rates were affected by mechanical properties such as failure strength of stitch threads or volume fraction of stitch thread. (Interlaminar fracture toughness result: higher value is expected than that stitched by Kevlar thread and the appropriate density will be determined. See Fig.11.)

In FY2003, a sub-component fatigue test using stiffened flat panel made by new method will be also conducted in NAL.

Fig. 11 Relationship between G_{IC}^{*1} and Stitch Density
^{*1} G_{IC} : Mode-I Strain Energy Release Rate

FULL-SCALE VERIFICATION TEST PLAN

The outline of full-scale verification test plans to be conducted by March 2004 is shown in Fig. 12-14.

Fig.12 Static load test plan for full-scale wing box structure

Fig.13 Static pressurization test plan for full-scale nose structure

Fig.14 Bird strike test plan for full-scale leading-edge structure

CONCLUSION

The results obtained at the end of March 2003 are,

- (1) The targets for weight reduction and part count reduction will be achieved, as shown in Table 1.
- (2) Conception and design with viable manufacturing technologies and their progress were assessed as proper by DER's, and a yearly assessment committee in JADC and NEDO.

We are trying to apply the technologies to an airplane in which the requirements for safety, reliability, airworthiness, and maintenance are the most rigorous. The introduction of an innovative structural method involves risks for its substantiation. In order to get substantiation, we have made a plan based on legal standards, accumulated characteristic data, full-scale components fabrication and tests. In the near future we hope that the fruit of the program will be applied to an actual airplane program primarily led by Japan or as an international joint enterprise.

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Table 1. Targets and Expected Results for Weight-& Part-Count Reduction

Portion	Weight Reduction	Part-Count Reduction
Nose Structure	Estimate 11% > Target 10%	Estimate 82% > Target 80%
Wing Box	27% > 15%	54% > 50%
Leading Edge	5% \geq 5%	88% > 80%

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